

Spectral Study of O-Benzo Quinone with Aqueous Westron as Organic Solvent

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Abstract

Excess Viscosity (η), specific acoustic Impedance (z), Rao's Constant (R), Shear's Relaxation Time (τ_s), Apparent molar adiabatic Compressibility (E_ϕ), and Excess Value (AE), Ultrasonic velocity, Density and viscosity measurements have been used to calculate Isentropic Compressibility (β_s), Intermolecular free length (L_f), Ultrasonic velocity (V), Density (ρ) of solution of O-Benzo Quinone in aqueous organic solvents such as WESTRON. In each case, ultrasound velocity increases and isentropic compressibility (β_s) decreases, Intermolecular free length (L_f), Density (ρ) increase and viscosity decreases with increases in molar concentration of O-Benzo Quinone. As usual, apparent molar adiabatic compressibility (E_ϕ) has been found to be negative. The result has been interpreted in terms of ion-solvent interaction on the basis of acoustic properties.

Keywords

Spectral Study, O-Benzo, Quinone, with Aqueous Westron, Organic Solvent.

Introduction

Quinones – Any class of Aromatic yellow compounds including several that are biologically important as coenzymes or acceptors or vitamins; use in making dyes. Quinones are a class of natural and synthetic compounds that have several beneficial effects. Quinones are electron carriers playing a role in photosynthesis. As vitamins, they represent a class of molecules preventing and treating several illnesses.

Objective of study

Present work covers an extensive survey of physico-chemical and solvolytic studies of some Quinones in aqueous organic solvents such as WESTRON system study at various temperatures (30°C, 35°C, 40°C) with various parameters.

Review of Literature

Qualitative determination of the degree of association in liquids to study the behavior of binary liquid mixture by measuring the sound velocity and related properties. Present work is reporting of the dissolved ion with water molecules and reporting the finding of a study of ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity measurement to calculate isentropic compressibility (β_s), intermolecular free length (L_f), molar volume (M_v), Rao's Constant (R), apparent molar adiabatic compressibility (E_ϕ), Shear's Relaxation Time (τ_s) of Quinone in solvent. Wave interferometric technique was employed for the measurement of ultrasonic Velocity. The Density and Viscosity were determined using a vibrating densitometer. The experiment was repeated and results were reproducible with experimental error of 0.0002 Kg/M³ and 0.0002 mPas respectively.

Result and Discussion

Present work covers an extensive survey of physico-chemical and solvolytic study of Quinone in aqueous organic solvent such as WESTRONE. All the system studied at various temperatures (30, 35, 40°C) we have reported ultrasound velocity (V) and Viscosity (η) of binary liquid mixture with experimental data. The following thermodynamic and acoustic properties like Isentropic compressibility (β), intermolecular free length (L_f), Molar Volume (M_v), Shear's Relaxation Time (τ) have been calculated.

Table 1: O-Benzo Quinone + WESTRONE at 30 ° C

Isentropic Compressibility of WESTRONE = 89.94×10^{12} dyne/cm²

C(mole/L)	ρ (gm/ml)	V (m/sec)	β_S (cm ² /dyne.10 ¹²)	$\beta_{SO}-\beta_S$ (cm ² /dyne.10 ¹²)	Γ (CP)	Γ_{SP} (CP)	τ_s (Sec)	Zx10 ³	R (m/sec)	S _u	L _r	$\beta_S-\beta_{SO}/C$ (10 ¹²)	M _w
0.0216	1.5646	1320	36.68	53.26	0.2693	0.0058	18.2856	2.0652	2822.54	9.8691	0.3822	-2465.6233	43.4496
0.0432	1.5667	1322	36.52	53.42	0.2693	0.0116	18.3104	2.0712	2827.87	9.8990	0.3813	-1236.5472	43.5379
0.0649	1.5689	1324	36.36	53.58	0.2689	0.0174	18.3348	2.0772	2833.20	9.9287	0.3805	-825.5665	43.7243
0.0865	1.5710	1326	36.20	53.74	0.2690	0.0233	18.3588	2.0832	2838.53	9.9553	0.3797	-621.2573	43.7874
0.1081	1.5732	1328	36.04	53.90	0.2690	0.0291	18.3823	2.0892	2843.87	9.9876	0.3788	-498.5875	43.8602
0.1297	1.5754	1330	35.89	54.05	0.2691	0.0349	18.4053	2.0952	2849.20	10.0169	0.3780	-416.7691	43.9376
0.1513	1.5775	1332	35.73	54.21	0.2691	0.0407	18.4279	2.1013	2854.54	10.0459	0.3772	-358.3058	44.0176
0.1730	1.5797	1334	35.57	54.37	0.2690	0.0465	18.4501	2.1073	2859.88	10.0748	0.3763	-314.2628	44.1358
0.1946	1.5819	1336	35.42	54.52	0.2690	0.0523	18.4719	2.1134	2865.23	10.1035	0.3755	-280.1766	44.2142
0.2162	1.5840	1338	35.26	54.68	0.2690	0.0582	18.4932	2.1194	2870.58	10.1320	0.3747	-252.8971	44.2940

Table 2: O-Benzo Quinone + WESTRONE at 35 ° C

Isentropic Compressibility of WESTRONE = 90.52×10^{12} dyne/cm²

C(mole/L)	ρ (gm/ml)	V(m/sec)	β_S (cm ² /dyne.10 ¹²)	$\beta_{SO}-\beta_S$ (cm ² /dyne.10 ¹²)	Γ (CP)	Γ_{SP} (CP)	τ_s (Sec)	Zx10 ³	R (m/sec)	S _u	L _r	$\beta_S-\beta_{SO}/C$ (10 ¹²)	M _w
0.0216	1.5509	1308	37.69	52.83	0.2922	0.0063	17.3198	2.0285	2789.32	9.7274	0.3909	-2445.8927	43.8348
0.0432	1.5530	1310	37.52	53.00	0.2921	0.0126	17.3511	2.0345	2794.63	9.7582	0.3899	-1226.8190	43.9246
0.0649	1.5552	1312	37.36	53.16	0.2918	0.0189	17.3819	2.0404	2799.95	9.7888	0.3890	-819.1817	44.1134
0.0865	1.5573	1314	37.19	53.33	0.2919	0.0252	17.4122	2.0464	2805.26	9.8192	0.3882	-616.5343	44.1779
0.1081	1.5595	1316	37.03	53.49	0.2920	0.0316	17.4419	2.0523	2810.58	9.8495	0.3873	-494.8616	44.2521
0.1297	1.5617	1318	36.86	53.66	0.2920	0.0379	17.4712	2.0583	2815.90	9.8796	0.3864	-413.7083	44.3310
0.1513	1.5638	1320	36.70	53.82	0.2920	0.0442	17.5000	2.0643	2821.23	9.9095	0.3856	-355.7197	44.4125
0.1730	1.5660	1322	36.54	53.98	0.2919	0.0505	17.5284	2.0702	2826.55	9.9392	0.3847	-312.0339	44.5324
0.1946	1.5682	1324	36.38	54.14	0.2919	0.0568	17.5562	2.0762	2831.88	9.9688	0.3839	-278.2240	44.6122
0.2162	1.5703	1326	36.22	54.30	0.2920	0.0631	17.5836	2.0822	2837.22	9.9982	0.3831	-251.1655	44.6935

Table 3: O-Benzo Quinone + WESTRONE at 40 ° C

Isentropic Compressibility of WESTRONE = 91.12×10^{12} dyne/cm²

C(mole/L)	ρ (gm/ml)	V(m/sec)	β_S (cm ² /dyne.10 ¹²)	$\beta_{SO}-\beta_S$ (cm ² /dyne.10 ¹²)	Γ (CP)	Γ_{SP} (CP)	τ_s (Sec)	Zx10 ³	R (m/sec)	S _u	L _r	$\beta_S-\beta_{SO}/C$ (10 ¹²)	M _w
0.0216	1.5281	1294	39.08	52.04	0.3145	0.0068	16.6996	1.9773	2738.47	9.5180	0.4014	-2409.1096	44.4911
0.0432	1.5302	1296	38.91	52.21	0.3145	0.0136	16.7367	1.9832	2743.76	9.5501	0.4005	-1208.6192	44.5837
0.0649	1.5324	1298	38.73	52.39	0.3140	0.0204	16.7733	1.9890	2749.05	9.5820	0.3996	-807.1939	44.7766
0.0865	1.5345	1300	38.56	52.56	0.3141	0.0272	16.8093	1.9949	2754.34	9.6138	0.3987	-607.6344	44.8434
0.1081	1.5367	1302	38.39	52.73	0.3142	0.0340	16.8448	2.0008	2759.64	9.6453	0.3978	-487.8152	44.9200
0.1297	1.5389	1304	38.22	52.90	0.3142	0.0408	16.8797	2.0067	2764.93	9.6767	0.3969	-407.8971	45.0014
0.1513	1.5410	1306	38.05	53.07	0.3143	0.0475	16.9144	2.0126	2770.23	9.7078	0.3960	-350.7909	45.0855
0.1730	1.5432	1308	37.88	53.24	0.3141	0.0543	16.9480	2.0185	2775.53	9.7388	0.3951	-307.7691	45.2085
0.1946	1.5454	1310	37.71	53.41	0.3141	0.0611	16.9814	2.0244	2780.84	9.7696	0.3942	-274.4730	45.2908
0.2162	1.5475	1312	37.54	53.58	0.3142	0.0679	17.0142	2.0303	2786.15	9.8002	0.3934	-247.8254	45.3746

Fig-1

Fig.-2

Fig.-3

Conclusion

The ultrasound velocity and concentration of the solution of O-Benzo Quinone in WESTRONE well on Fig. 1-4. The ultrasound velocity of the solution of O-Benzo Quinone in WESTRONE increases with increasing Molar Concentration of Solvents.

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